

Using ETL for Optimizing Business Intelligence Success in Multiple Investment Combinations

¹Nitin Anand, ²Nitesh Kumar, ³Jnyanaranjan Dash, ⁴Dipa Patra

¹AIACTR, CSE Deptt, New Delhi, India, proudtobeanindiannitin@gmail.com

²School of Computer Engineering, KIIT University, Bhubaneswar, Orissa, India, niteshkumarkiit@gmail.com

³School of Computer Engineering, KIIT University, Bhubaneswar, Orissa, India, jnyanaranjan@hotmail.com

⁴School of Computer Engineering, KIIT University, Bhubaneswar, Orissa, India, dipa24.patra@gmail.com

Abstract

Business Intelligence (BI) refers to technologies, tools, and practices for collecting, integrating, analyzing, and presenting large volumes of information to enable better decision making. BI systems combine data gathering, data storage, and knowledge management with analytical tools to present complex internal and competitive information to planners and decision makers. An important part of BI systems is a well performing implementation of the Extract, Transform, and Load (ETL) process. This paper reports the results of a case study that investigated the nature of DW/BI development.

Keywords: Business Intelligence (BI), Data Warehouse, Decision Support System, Extract, Transform, and Load, ETL Design.

1. Introduction

Business intelligence (BI) has gained wide recognition in the last few years [5]. It also got high business impact and is seen as a key enabler for increasing value and performance" [6]. Unsurprisingly, the progress of BI is monitored by management and IT consultants [7]. It is recognized as having a high relevance for the profit of businesses [8]. Business intelligence is a rather new discipline with a lot of research activity. Even though the term has been coined in 1958 [9], the number of published papers has risen considerably in the last few years. The rapid progress has also brought a high level of heterogeneity [10]; this causes both problems for businesses and offers research opportunities. One important component of BI is the Extract, Transform and Load (ETL) process. It describes the gathering of data from various sources (extract), its modification to match a desired state (transformation) and its import into a database or data warehouse (load). ETL processes take up to 80% of the effort in BI projects [11]. A high performance is thereby vital to be able to process large amounts of data and to have an up-to-date database. The term ETL is known for a while [12] and the relevant market is already divided by a number of major players [13]. While open source tools are competitive with commercial software in many areas, there is little published work on open source ETL tools .even though the practical relevance is given. Open Source BI tools recently gained more attention [7] and start to compete with commercial solutions [14]. Therefore, we present an analysis of open

source ETL tools. We especially focus on the performance, which is a main criterion for ETL processes. Well performing open source tools could be alternatives to proprietary solutions. The contributions of our paper are the summary of the background, the considerations on how to design a study for performance comparison and the actual results including our decision advise. Moreover, with a general discussion of the study we contribute to the body of BI knowledge. There are main types of BI – strategic, tactical, and operational (see Table1). Strategic BI is used for managing long-term business plans and goals [2]. Executives and senior managers use the high-level business performance metrics (sometimes called key performance indicators, or KPIs) produced by strategic BI to track how well the business is doing against long-term business goals such as growing market share, reducing costs, and increasing revenues. As business initiatives are launched (marketing campaigns, new products, for example) to help align actual business performance with planned performance, tactical BI analytics are employed by senior managers, business analysts, and line-of-business (LOB) managers to measure and optimize the performance of those initiatives. This tactical BI analyzes business operations over a period of days, weeks, or months.

	Strategic BI	Tactical BI	Operational Right Time BI
Business Focus	Achieve long-term business goals	Manage tactical initiatives to achieve strategic goals	Manage and optimize daily business operations
Primary Users	Executives and business analysts	Senior managers, business analysts, and LOB managers	LOB managers, LOB users, and operational systems
Time Frame	Months to years	Days to weeks to months	Intra-day
Data	Historical metrics (KPIs)	Historical metrics	Right-time metrics

Table1. Types of BI

Operational BI is concerned with managing and optimizing daily business operations. It delivers the right information at the right time to the right business users to enable them to react rapidly to solve business problems and satisfy new business requirements. It helps organizations work smarter and become more agile, which in turn enables them to be more competitive and to improve customer satisfaction. Fraud detection, risk management, customer segmentation, network management, and inventory management are examples of operational processes that can be improved using operational BI.

2. Background

BI success is related to the positive value such as improved profitability, reduced costs and improved efficiency which an organization obtains from its BI investment and fit between an organization’s BI and its goals. A successful project must be completed within budget and according to schedule while functioning as required [17]. Since BI system investment effort is a costly, time-consuming, resource intensive process, there is a common view among scholars which it is difficult to measure its influential factors then there has been little empirical research about the critical success factors (CSFs) impacting the investment of such systems [19]. This is because the study of BI systems is a relatively new area that has primarily been driven by the IT industry and vendors, and thus there is limited rigorous and systematic research into identifying the CSFs of BI system investment [18]. However, no study has provided an in-depth analysis of BIS success. Consequently, our study’s main objective is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the interrelationships between BIS success dimensions. Functionality of BI has been depicted in Fig 1 .

Fig1. Functionality of BI

3. What Does BI Do?

BI assists in strategic and operational decision making [15]. A Gartner survey ranked the strategic use of BI in the following order [16]:

- Corporate performance management
- Optimizing customer relations, monitoring business activity, and traditional decision support
- Packaged standalone BI applications for specific operations or strategies
- Management reporting of business intelligence

One implication of this ranking is that merely reporting the performance of a firm and its competitors, which is the strength of many existing software packages, is not enough. A second implication is that too many firms still view business intelligence (like DSS and EIS before it) as an inward looking function. Business intelligence is a natural outgrowth of a series of previous systems designed to support decision making. The emergence of the data warehouse as a repository, the advances in data cleansing that lead to a single truth, the greater capabilities of hardware and software, and the boom of Internet technologies that provided the prevalent user interface all combine to create a richer business intelligence environment than was available previously. BI pulls information from many other systems. Figure 2 depicts some of the information systems that are used by BI.

Fig2: BI Relation to Other Information Systems

where: OLAP = On-line data processing, CRM=customer relationship management, DSS= decision support systems, GIS = geographic information systems.

The different levels in an organization (strategic, management, and operational) have different decision-making requirements. Decisions can be structured, semi-structured or unstructured.

The structured decisions are clustered at the operational level of the organization, and unstructured decisions at the strategic level. Management information systems (MIS) provide information on firm performance to help managers monitor and control the business, often in the form of fixed regularly scheduled reports based on data summarized from the firm's transaction processing systems (TPS). MIS support structured decisions and some semi-structured decisions. DSS combine data, sophisticated analytical models and tools, and user-friendly software into a single powerful system that can support semi-structured and unstructured decision making [21, 22,23]. The main components of the DSS are the DSS database, the user interface, and the DSS software system (Figure 3). The DSS database is a collection of current data from a number of applications and current data from a number of applications and groups. Alternatively, the DSS database may be a data warehouse that integrates the enterprise data sources and maintains historical data.

Fig3. Main Components of DSS [20]

4. Business Processes Warehousing

In this section, we present the main concepts related to business process warehousing, the existing challenges, and the approach we follow for populating a process data warehouse [4].

4.1 Challenges

There are three main challenges in business process warehousing: genericity, abstraction, and data independence.

Genericity. Developing ad hoc, process-specific solutions for warehousing process data is not a sustainable model. Thus, one of the main challenges is that of developing a general and reusable solution for process data warehousing, applicable to most or all the processes in an enterprise. Furthermore, our approach can be extended to other applications that have similar characteristics.

Abstraction. A typical process executed in the underlying IT systems is very detailed and consists of hundreds of steps, including manual operations (e.g., scanning invoices), database transactions, and application invocations. However, having visibility (reporting, analytics, etc.) at this level of detail is confusing for analysts who have a much higher level abstract view of the process. The common wisdom is that business analysts and managers perceive a process as being composed of approximately 5 to 7 steps. Service level agreements (SLA's) and key performance indicators (KPI's) are also defined on abstracted views of a process.

Data Independence. The infrastructure underlying the process execution is subject to dynamic changes and it is important to shield the process warehouse from those changes. For example, the infrastructure that handles the notification of acceptance of an order could evolve from database technology where a purchase order record is updated, to a more proactive service-oriented technology where a message is sent to a web service that handles the notification. This change should not affect the process warehouse schema or the mappings to its tables. The challenge is in developing a solution that provides this kind of independence.

4.2 Process Data Warehouse Model

The process data warehouse model was designed to be generic to support the analysis of arbitrary business processes, and to support the computation of a large variety of process metrics [3].

5. Success Factors for Data Warehouse and Business Intelligence Systems

Data Warehouse (DW) and Business Intelligence (BI) systems are among the most important IT-based systems in organizations. The decisions made using these systems can fundamentally affect an organization's nature and performance.

Factor	Description	References
Committed and informed executive sponsor	A senior executive should be responsible for overall guidance of the project, allocating resources and representing the project to the executive team and board.	McBride (1997), Poon and Wagner (2001), Sammon and Finnegan (2000), Watson et al. (2004), Wixom and Watson (2001)
Widespread management support	DW/BI should be business driven with widespread management support. This helps manage the change process and overcome resistance.	Rainer and Watson (1995), Sammon and Finnegan (2000), Wixom and Watson (2001)
Appropriate team skills	Staff in the client organization and external suppliers should have appropriate knowledge, skills and experience.	Poon and Wagner (2001), Salmeron and Herrero (2005), Sammon and Finnegan (2000), Wixom and Watson (2001)
Appropriate technology	There should be a high degree of organizational fit with the DW/BI hardware and software.	Poon and Wagner (2001), Salmeron and Herrero (2005), Sammon and Finnegan (2000), Wixom and Watson (2001)
Adequate resources	There should be adequate funding of hardware, software and human resources.	Lindsey and Frolick (2003), Sammon and Finnegan (2000), Wixom and Watson (2001)
Effective data management	Operational data sources should be available. ETL applications should ensure currency, consistency, and accuracy. The data model should be flexible and extensible	Poon and Wagner (2001), Rainer and Watson (1995), Sammon and Finnegan (2000), Watson et al. (2004), Wixom and Watson (2001)
Clear link with business objectives	The project should have a clear link with the business's strategies and be economically justified in terms of its business value	Poon and Wagner (2001), Rainer and Watson (1995), Watson et al. (2004)
Well-defined information and systems requirements	Despite the difficulty of defining executives' requirements, the project should have an accepted definition of what is required from the system	Salmeron and Herrero (2005), Rainer and Watson (1995), Poon and Wagner (2001), Watson et al. (2004)
Evolutionary development	A successful DW/BI system should be developed iteratively with strong user involvement, evolving towards an effective application set	McBride (1997), Poon and Wagner (2001), Salmeron and Herrero (2005), Sammon and Finnegan (2000), Wixom and Watson (2001)
Management of project scope	The scope of a project can increase significantly. This can stretch project resources	Lindsey and Frolick (2003), Rainer and Watson (1995)

Table2. Critical Success Factors for DW/BI Systems [3]

6. Conclusion

BI technology has become a very popular globally among enterprise executives, IT professionals, and BI vendors. Enterprises have compiled huge volumes of disparate data stored and accessible from a variety of information systems that have evolved since the 1960s. None of the traditional information systems architecture has been totally integrated into the whole enterprise. In other words, the Standardized Business Intelligence Architecture is the first to objectively incorporate industry standards along with basic management practices. BI uses both structured and semi-structured data. The former is much easier to search but the latter contains the information needed for analysis and decision making. For structured data, many BI tools exist for acquisition, integration, cleanup, search, analysis, and delivery. Further work is needed, however, to integrate these tools and to provide actionable information. BI tools for semi structured data, on the other hand, are not yet mature. However, significant work is being done in industry to deal with semi-structured data [24], [25].

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